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LINGUISTIC TERMS IN CONTEMPORARY TEXTBOOKS OF CROATIAN LANGUAGE

Abstract: *Since 2019, when the Croatian language subject curriculum was introduced, until today, new textbooks of Croatian have been written, and the aim of this paper is to investigate how consistent they are in the use of linguistic terminology. Previous research has pointed to the lack of uniformity and consistency in the use of linguistic terminology in Croatian language textbooks, which is reflected, among other things, in many pairs and sequences of synonyms, causing difficulties in school practice. In the first phase of the research, which is presented in this paper, all primary school textbooks for grades 5-8 were analyzed, focusing on the terms at the phonological, morphological, syntactic, lexicological, and orthographical levels. The results of the textbooks analysis were compared with the terminology in contemporary school grammar books and Croatian orthography and spelling books, with the 2006 Primary School Curriculum, and with the 2019 Croatian language subject curriculum entitled the Curriculum of the Subject Croatian Language for Primary Schools and Grammar Schools. Although certain different linguistic terms can be found in new textbooks at all mentioned levels, it can still be concluded that contemporary textbooks are more consistent than previous textbooks regarding the use of linguistic terms.*

Keywords: *Croatian language, naming linguistic terms, primary school textbooks*

INTRODUCTION

Although various teaching aids have been used in the classroom and education technology has evolved (this referring especially to digital tools development), Croatian language textbooks still have an important role in language education, while in planning and conducting classes, they are a support to the teacher. In terms of language, textbooks are required to be written in exemplary and age-appropriate standard language, and in terms of teaching content, they should be reliable sources.

The teaching contents of Croatian language textbooks include, among other things, the linguistic terms that students acquire, and uniformity and consistency in naming these terms in textbooks would be preferred. However, when it comes to the use of linguistic terminology in Croatian textbooks, we can see the opposite, i.e. inconsistency at all linguistic levels, including orthography, morphology, syntax, word formation, and vocabulary (cf. Hudeček and Mihaljević 2020, p. 8). Thus, the analysis of high school and some primary school textbooks conducted by Hudeček, Mihaljević, and Vidović on the then approved textbooks fifteen years ago (2006) clearly showed many pairs and sequences of synonyms in the basic linguistic terminology, which causes difficulties in school practice: “Class and subject teachers, authors of high school textbooks, textbook reviewers, members of school textbook evaluation committees, members of Croatian language

competition committees, members of working groups, and state graduation advisors regularly warn of the inconsistency in the use of basic linguistic terminology at all levels: using synonyms and near-synonyms, using different terms in different textbooks, using different terms in primary and secondary schools, and using different terms in higher education textbooks.” (Hudeček and Mihaljević, 2020, p. 2)

The inconsistency in the use of linguistic terminology in textbooks is partly due to the fact that even in professional literature, in grammar books and orthography and spelling manuals which serve as sources for writing textbooks, the terminology is not uniform and systematic. As Hudeček, Mihaljević, and Vidović point out, experts “may have different attitudes to and views on certain issues”, which may be reflected in the use of the terms, these views nevertheless “should not be reflected in textbooks used at the same time in different schools or even different grades of the same school” and, they conclude, “the terminology used in textbooks should be uniform” (2006, p. 120).

In the meantime, the Institute of Croatian Language and Linguistics, due to the need to systematize linguistic terminology, launched the project *Croatian Linguistic Terminology – Jena*, which ran from May 24, 2019 to December 23, 2020, after which it has been implemented as an internal project of the Institute and a part of the wider project *Croatian Special Field Terminology – Struna* (cf. Mihaljević, Hudeček and Jozić, 2020, p. IV). Furthermore, the currents of the education system reform led to the introduction of the *Curriculum Reform*, which was introduced as an experimental program of the Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Croatia in the school year 2018/2019. At the moment of writing this paper, the entire vertical of the education system is covered by the reform. With the 2019 adoption of the national curriculum, officially called the *National Curriculum*, the previous plans and programs ceased to be in force, and this required the development of new school textbooks according to the reform requirements. Thus, in line with the Croatian language subject curriculum entitled the *Curriculum of the Subject Croatian Language for Primary Schools and Grammar Schools*, all new textbooks for the Croatian language, which are used in primary and secondary schools, have been developed to date. The question arises: Do they include many synonyms in linguistic terminology or have the inconsistencies been eliminated, given that the problem has been noticed and the first results of *Jena* already known? We therefore consider it worthwhile to answer this question, that is, we consider it valuable to investigate the level of uniformity in the use of linguistic terminology in the new generation of Croatian language textbooks.

METHODOLOGY

The research will take place in two phases. In the first research phase, which is presented in this paper, all primary school Croatian textbooks for grades 5-8 were analyzed, including all six sets of textbooks, which makes a total of 24 textbooks (see *Table 1*). The second phase of the research will include high school textbooks. Therefore, a complete insight into the research problem will be gained only after the second research phase.

In the analysis of linguistic terms in the textbooks, special attention was paid to those terms that are named differently in textbooks, language manuals, and program documents which serve as sources for writing textbooks. The results obtained from the completed textbook analysis were then compared with the terminology in the following grammar books: *Gramatika hrvatskoga jezika za gimnazije i visoka učilišta* (2005) by Silić and Pranjković, *Gramatika hrvatskoga jezika: priručnik za osnovno jezično obrazovanje* (2016) by Težak and Babić, *Školska gramatika hrvatskoga jezika* by Sanda Ham (2017), and *Hrvatska školska gramatika* by Lana Hudeček and Milica Mihaljević (2019) and the terminology in the following orthography and spelling books: *Hrvatski školski pravopis* (2005) by Babić, Ham, and Moguš, *Hrvatski pravopis* by Lada Badurina, Ivan Marković, and Krešimir Mićanović (2008), *Hrvatski pravopis usklađen sa zaključcima Vijeća za normu hrvatskoga standardnog jezika* (2010) by Babić and Moguš, and *Hrvatski pravopis* published by Institut za hrvatski jezik i jezikoslovlje (Jozić, 2013), which was approved for use in schools. The results of the textbooks analysis were also compared with the 2006 *Primary School Curriculum* and with the 2019 Croatian language subject curriculum entitled the *Curriculum of the Subject Croatian Language for Primary Schools and Grammar Schools*.

Table 1.*Research sample – primary school textbooks*

Textbook	Author(s)	Publisher
<i>Hrvatska krijesnica</i> 5, 6, 7, 8	Kovač, Slavica and Jukić, Mirjana	Ljevak
<i>Hrvatske jezične niti</i> 5, 6, 7, 8	Miloloža, Sanja; Cikuša, Rada; Šimić, Davor and Petrović, Bernardina	Alfa
<i>Hrvatski bez granica</i> 5, 6, 7, 8	Levak, Julijana; Močibob, Iva; Sandalić, Jasmina; Petto, Ida and Budija, Ksenija	Školska knjiga
<i>Hrvatski za</i> 5/ <i>Petica</i> , 6/ <i>Šestica</i> , 7/ <i>Sedmica</i> , 8/ <i>Osmica</i>	Družijanić-Hajdarević, Ela; Greblički-Miculinović, Diana; Matošević, Krunoslav and Romić, Zrinka	Profil Klett
<i>Naš hrvatski</i> 5, 6, 7, 8	Šojat, Anita	Školska knjiga
<i>Volim hrvatski</i> 5, 6, 7, 8	Rihtarić, Anđelka; Latin, Sanja and Majić, Žana	Školska knjiga

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TERMS AT THE PHONOLOGICAL LEVEL

It was found that in the analyzed textbooks, most of the names for linguistic terms are uniform at the phonological level, including: *sibilarizacija*, *palatalizacija*, *jotacija*, *nepostojani a*, *nepostojani e*, *naglasnica*, *nenaglasnica*, *prednaglasnica*, *zanaglasnica*, *slog*, *samoglasnik*, *naglasak*, *rečenična intonacija*, *kratkouzlazni*, *dugosilazni*, *dugouzlazni*, *ikavski govor*, *ekavski govor*.¹

Mild inconsistency has been noticed in the textbooks *Hrvatska krijesnica* 7 (p. 71) and *Hrvatske jezične niti* (p. 103) when naming prosodic unit length *duljina* or *dužina*. We should note that other textbooks as well as the subject curriculum and the *Primary School Curriculum* (2006) do not mention these names, which excludes further comparison at this level, but it is worth to see how they are named in grammar manuals. Namely, Ham (2017, p. 28) uses the term *duljina*, while Silić and Pranjković (2005, p. 18), Težak and Babić (2016, p. 81), Hudeček and Mihaljević (2019, p. 32) use the term *dužina* in this context. The alternation between the names *duljina* and *dužina* has also been found in professional literature. In the 1960s (1963, p. 63), Babić discussed these names, emphasizing that both names were correct, but he still preferred the name *dužina* because it was in line with the systematic word formation. It has been noticed that the name *dužina* also prevails in the analyzed grammar books as well as in the grammar written by Barić et al. (2005, p. 69). Therefore, the textbook *Hrvatske jezične niti* 7 follows the prevailing current that gives preference to the use of the name *dužina* as a prosodic unit.

Furthermore, the textbook *Hrvatske jezične niti* 7 uses a synonym pair for the accent marked with ('): *kratkosilazni/brzi* (short falling/quick), while other textbooks use only the term *kratkosilazni*. The subject curriculum (2019) and *Primary School Curriculum* (2006) do not contain these terms. Most authors

¹ Sibilarization, palatalization, jotation, vowel – zero alternations (movable a, movable e), accentuated word, clitic, proclitic, enclitic, syllable, vowel, accent, sentence intonation, short rising, long falling, long raising, Ikavian speech, Ekavian speech.

of grammar books use the term *kratkosilazni*, including Silić and Pranjković (2005, p. 18), Težak and Babić (2016, p. 81), Ham (2017, p. 26), Hudeček and Mihaljević (2019, p. 31), but Barić et al. (2005, p. 68), for example, use the same synonym pair as the one from the textbook *Hrvatske jezične niti* 7.

Considering the types of speech according to the reflexes of yat, in the textbooks there is a lack of uniformity in the name for *Jekavian/(I)jekavian speech* as a reflection of the two-vowel reflex /ie/, which in long syllables reflects into *ije*, and in short into *je*. Three textbooks mention the name *(i)jekavski govor* ((I)jekavian speech), two textbooks mention *jekavski govor* (Jekavian speech), and one textbook records both names (see *Table 2*). These names are not mentioned in the subject curriculum and the *Primary School Curriculum*. In the grammar book by Težak and Babić, the name *jekavski govor* is used (2016, p. 18), and this name is also preferred in professional literature (e.g. Babić, 1995, p. 20), but obviously not in textbooks that mostly use the name *(i)jekavski govor*.

Table 2.

Names for Jekavian/(I)jekavian speech in the analyzed textbooks²

<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 6</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 5</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 6</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 5 (part 1)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 5</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 5</i>
(i)jekavski (112)	jekavski (15)	(i)jekavski govor (31)	jekavski (47)	(i)jekavski govor (10)	jekavski /(i)jekavski govor (9)

TERMS AT THE MORPHOLOGICAL LEVEL

Regarding the names for the terms in primary school textbooks which are related to the morphological level, in the compared language manuals the differences have been noticed in naming exclamations *uzvik/usklik* as parts of speech, personal pronouns *osobne/lične zamjenice*, category of person *osoba/lice* (*glagolska osoba/glagolsko lice* as a verbal category of person), and in naming the participants in the communication situation: speaker/interlocutor/non-speaker are called *govorna/sugovorna/negovorna osoba, govoritelj/sugovoritelj/negovoritelj*, and *govornik/sugovornik/negovornik*.

Silić and Pranjković (2005) and Ham (2017) prefer the name *uzvik*, making a difference between exclamations as parts of speech and the category of exclamation (*uskličnost*). In contrast, Težak and Babić (2016), Hudeček and Mihaljević (2019) use the name *usklik* in their grammar books. Lazić and Mihaljević (2020), based on the corpus analysis of *Jena*, the analysis of dictionaries, orthography and spelling books, older grammar books, and discourses of school practice, argue that preference should be given to the name *usklik*, which is also used in the *Primary School Curriculum* (2006, p. 35), while in the subject curriculum this part of speech is not explicitly mentioned. The analyzed primary school textbooks are uniform and use the name *usklik*.

In the last decade of the 20th century, advocating for the revival of older Croatian names, Croatian philologists such as Stjepan Babić (1995), Mile Mamić (1997), and Sanda Ham (1998, 2002) reintroduced

² In all tables, when referring to a specific name for the term, the corresponding textbook page number is given in parentheses. Moreover, the textbook *Hrvatski bez granica* consists of two parts for all grades, and the tables indicate which part they refer to (part 1 or part 2).

the names *osobna zamjenica* (personal pronoun) and *glagolska osoba* (person as a verbal category of person), arguing that these names include all three persons, ‘lica’, they are found in the oldest Croatian dictionaries, *lice* and *osoba* are synonymous in grammatical terminology but in different languages (*osoba* in Croatian, *lice* in Serbian), and the modern Croatian paradigm related to linguistic terminology is based on the concept of *osoba*, and not *lice* (*osoba*, *osobno*, *neosobno* meaning person, personal, impersonal) (Babić, 1995; Ham, 2002). Linguists such as Ivo Pranjković (1995) and Branka Tafra (1999) disagree with this, differentiating the grammatical category *lice* from the semantic category *osoba* and consequently the corresponding names for the terms, thus opposing attempts to introduce the names *osobna zamjenica* and *glagolska osoba* into grammatical terminology. The name *osobna zamjenica* was also problematized by Mirko Peti (1998), who stated that the name was not appropriate due to the syntactic position of the subject from which its ‘lično’ značenje (personal meaning) derives, thus syntactic relations are based on *lice* and not *osoba*. Therefore, we can speak of *lične zamjenice only*, and not of *osobne zamjenice*.

In accordance with different points of view, the names *osobne zamjenice* and *glagolska osoba* have been confirmed in the grammar books by Težak and Babić (2016) and Ham (2017), while the names *lične zamjenice* and *glagolsko lice* have been used in the grammar book by Silić and Pranjković (2005). In contrast, Hudeček and Mihaljević (2019) use the names *osobne zamjenice* and *glagolsko lice*. In the 2006 *Primary School Curriculum* (2006, pp. 38, 39), the names *osobne zamjenice* and *glagolska osoba* are used.³ The 2019 *Curriculum* uses the name *osobne zamjenice* (2019, p. 47) and *lice* as a morphological category.⁴

In all analyzed textbooks, the name *osobne zamjenice* is used, but in one of them both names are found, i.e. *osobne zamjenice* and *lične zamjenice* (see Table 3). The name *glagolska osoba* is used in four textbooks, and the name *glagolsko lice* in two textbooks (see Table 3). In the analyzed textbooks, thus, the name *glagolska osoba* predominates, although the official document which served as a source for writing new textbooks uses the name *lice*.

Table 3.

Names for personal pronouns and verbal category of person in the analyzed textbooks

<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 5</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 5</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 5</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 5 (part 1)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 5</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 5</i>
glagolska osoba (82)	glagolsko lice (56)	glagolsko lice (68)	glagolska osoba (117)	glagolska osoba (65)	glagolska osoba (77)
<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 6</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 6</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 6</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 6 (part 1)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 6</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 6</i>
osobna zamjenica (105)	osobna zamjenica (76)	osobna/lična zamjenica (44)	osobna zamjenica (51)	osobna zamjenica (21)	osobna zamjenica (43)

³ Cf.: “sprezati glagole u prezentu prema morfološkim obilježjima (osoba i broj)” (“to conjugate verbs in the present tense according to morphological features (person and number)”) (*Primary School Curriculum*, 2006, p. 39).

⁴ Cf.: “morfološke kategorije: rod, broj, padež, lice i vrijeme” (“morphological categories: gender, number, case, person, and tense”) (*Curriculum of the Subject Croatian Language for Primary Schools and Grammar Schools*, 2019, pp. 24 and 28).

Regarding teaching personal pronouns, it is also necessary to analyze how the persons involved in the communication situation are called in the textbooks. In almost all textbooks, there is a syntagm with the component of *osoba* (person), whether it is an attributive two-word expression (*govorna/sugovorna/negovorna osoba*; speaker, interlocutor, non-speaker) or an explanatory phrase (*osoba koja govori / kojoj se govori / o kojoj se govori*; person who speaks / is spoken to / is spoken about) which indicates the role of the person in communication situation (see *Table 4*). It is interesting that one of the six textbooks, namely *Hrvatske jezične niti*, does not mention this name at all, i.e. it does not analyze personal pronouns in the context of speaker, interlocutor, non-speaker. Furthermore, three textbooks are uniform and use the attributive syntagm *govorna/sugovorna/negovorna osoba*, which in two textbooks was supplemented by the already mentioned explanatory phrase (*osoba koja govori / (o) kojoj se govori*) and one-word expressions *govornik, sugovornik, negovornik* (speaker, interlocutor, non-speaker), which can be seen in *Table 4*. It is already clear that there is an inconsistency in the use of the analyzed names for linguistic terms. In addition, the grammar book by Hudeček and Mihaljević, along with the mentioned sequences of synonyms, offers one-word names *govoritelj, sugovoritelj, and negovoritelj* (speaker, interlocutor, and non-speaker) (2019, pp. 227, 231, and 241). On the other hand, Peti warns of the different meaning of the words *govornik* and *govoritelj* in terms of the distinction between *lice* and *osoba*, i.e. the morphosyntactic and pragmalinguistic concepts: “Instead, initially, as a ‘person who speaks’ (‘osoba koja govori’) followed by a ‘being who speaks’ (‘čeljade koje govori’), today, in the same sense, first person (prvo lice) is defined as ‘the one who speaks’, and this is how, as a *sui generis* speaker (*govornik sui generis*), it differs from a real person (*osoba*) who, as a speaker (*govoritelj*), organizes his speech in the form of that first person (prvo lice). What is said about the first person can also be applied to the second and third.” (1998, p. 41)

Silić and Pranjaković (2005, pp. 117–118) follow this opinion in their grammar book, while Ham (2017, p. 67) uses the names *govorna, sugovorna, and negovorna osoba*, i.e. the same expressions as those in the analyzed textbooks. Even philologists do not agree on the names for persons involved in a communication situation. Regarding education policy documents, these names are not explicitly mentioned in the subject curriculum (2019), so it is not possible to determine their terminological guidelines. The *Primary School Curriculum* includes the names *govornik, sugovornik, and negovornik* (2006, p. 35). In conclusion, newer grammatical currents introduce one-word names with the suffix *-telj*, which are not accepted in the contemporary textbook discourse, while names with the suffix *-(n)ik* are more common in the Croatian grammatical and textbook tradition.

Table 4.

Names for persons involved in the communication situation in the analyzed textbooks

<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 6</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 6</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 6</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 6 (part 1)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 6</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 6</i>
govorna osoba (42)	/	govorna osoba (44)	govornik, govorna osoba, osoba koja govori (51)	govorna osoba (22)	govornik, govorna osoba, osoba koja govori (43)
sugovorna osoba (42)	/	sugovorna osoba (44)	sugovornik, sugovorna osoba, osoba	sugovorna osoba (22)	sugovornik, sugovorna osoba, osoba

			kojoj se govori (51)		kojoj se govori (43)
sugovorna osoba (42)	/	sugovorna osoba (44)	negovornik, negovorna osoba, osoba o kojoj se govori (51)	sugovorna osoba (22)	negovornik, negovorna osoba, osoba o kojoj se govori (43)

As for the other differences related to the use of morphological terms in textbooks, we draw attention to some less pronounced ones. Thus, in all analyzed textbooks, the name *čestica* (particle) is used to denote a part of speech, while in one textbook, *Hrvatska krijesnica 5*, the older name *riječca* is mentioned as well (2019, p. 43). In five textbooks, there is a term *gramatička obilježja* (grammatical features), and in one textbook, there is a synonymous term *gramatička kategorija* (grammatical category). When naming verb moods, all textbooks include the names *imperativ*, *kondicional*, *kondicional prvi*, and *kondicional drugi* (imperative, conditional, first conditional, and second conditional). Four textbooks mention also *zapovjedni način* (commanding mood), three textbooks mention *pogodbeni način* (conditional mood), while two textbooks mention *kondicional sadašnji* and *kondicional prošli* (present conditional and past conditional) (see *Table 5*).

Table 5.

Some less pronounced differences in the use of terms in the analyzed textbooks

<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 5</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 5</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 5</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 5</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 5</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 5</i>
čestica, riječca (43)	čestica (79)	čestica (56)	čestica (100, part 1)	čestica (28)	čestica (34)
gramatička obilježja/ gramatičke kategorije (52)	gramatička obilježja (53)	gramatička obilježja (93)	/	gramatička obilježja (33)	gramatička obilježja (39)
infinitiv (92)	infinitiv (56)	infinitiv (70)	infinitiv (119, part 1)	infinitiv (71)	neodređeni glagolski oblik/infiniti v (81)
<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 6</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 6</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 6</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 6 (part 2)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 6</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 6</i>
imperativ/ zapovjedni način (90)	imperativ (126)	imperativ/ zapovjedni način (123)	imperativ/ zapovjedni način (119)	imperativ (61)	imperativ/ zapovjedni način (88)

kondicional/ pogodbeni način (94)	kondicional (127)	kondicional (126)	kondicional/ pogodbeni način (127)	kondicional (64)	kondicional/ pogodbeni način (92)
kondicional prvi (95)	kondicional prvi (127)	kondicional prvi/ kondicional sadašnji (127)	kondicional prvi (128)	kondicional prvi (64)	kondicional prvi/ kondicional sadašnji (92)
kondicional drugi (95)	kondicional drugi (127)	kondicional drugi/prošli (127)	kondicional drugi (128)	kondicional drugi (64)	kondicional drugi/prošli (94)

Taking into account the above-mentioned, in all analyzed textbooks, the following names are completely uniform (listed in their canonical form): *imenica, glagol, zamjenica, pridjev, broj* (part of speech), *prilog, prijedlog, veznik, uzvik, niječnica, padež, rod, broj* (grammatical), *imenske riječi, promjenjive riječi, nepromjenjive riječi, nominativ, genitiv, dativ, akuzativ, vokativ, lokativ, instrumental, perfekt, krnji perfekt, prezent, futur prvi, futur drugi, aorist, imperfekt, pluskvamperfekt, glagolski pridjev radni, glagolski pridjev trpni, jednostavan glagolski oblik, složen glagolski oblik, osnova, nastavak, pomoćni glagol, pozitiv, komparativ, superlativ, sklonidba/deklinacija, sprezanje/konjugacija, stupnjevanje/komparacija, glagolski vid, dvovidni glagol, vidski par, vidski parnjak, svršeni glagol, nesvršeni glagol, prijelazni glagol, neprijelazni glagol, povratni glagol, glagolska imenica, glagolski način, brojeva imenica, glavni broj, redni broj, opća imenica, vlastita imenica, zbirna imenica, posvojna zamjenica, povratna zamjenica, povratno-posvojna zamjenica, pokazna zamjenica, upitna zamjenica, odnosna zamjenica, neodređena zamjenica, glagolski prilog sadašnji, glagolski prilog prošli.*⁵

Regarding synonym pairs in the names *sklonidba/deklinacija* (declension), *sprezanje/konjugacija* (conjugation), and *stupnjevanje/komparacija* (comparison), it should be noted that the use of the recommended Croatian term (*sklonidba, sprezanje, stupnjevanje*) is consistent in all textbooks, while the international terms (*deklinacija, konjugacija, komparacija*) appear in addition when defining the term and when first mentioned in the textbook, which is typical of school practice (Hudeček, Mihaljević, and Vidović, 2006).

TERMS AT THE SYNTACTIC LEVEL

Regarding names for the terms at the syntactic level, the inconsistency is mostly visible in the use of synonym pairs. When listing parts of a sentence in one textbook, there is a synonym pair *predikat/prirok* (predicate). Thus, out of six textbooks for grade 7, only the textbook *Hrvatska krijesnica 7* includes the

⁵ Noun, verb, pronoun, adjective, number (part of speech), adverb, preposition, conjunction, exclamation, negative word, case, gender, number (grammatical), nominals, inflected words, non-inflected words, nominative, genitive, dative, accusative, vocative, locative, instrumental, perfect tense, truncated perfect tense, present tense, first future tense, second future tense, aorist tense, imperfect tense, plusquamperfect tense, 1-participle, past participle, simple verb form, complex verb form, base, suffix, auxiliary verb, positive, comparative, superlative, declension, conjugation, adjective comparison, verbal aspect, biaspectual verb, aspectual pair, aspectual pair component, perfective verb, imperfective verb, transitive verb, intransitive verb, reflexive verb, verbal noun, verb mood, numerical noun, cardinal number, ordinal number, common noun, proper noun, collective noun, possessive pronoun, reflexive pronoun, reflexive-possessive pronoun, demonstrative pronoun, interrogative pronoun, relative pronoun, indefinite pronoun, present verbal adverb, past verbal adverb.

Croatian name for the predicate (see *Table 6*). Similarly, in Silić and Pranjković's grammar book (2005, p. 285), there are two names, a loanword and a Croatian name, while in other grammar books (including Težak and Babić, 2016, p. 229; Ham, 2017, p. 171; Hudeček and Mihaljević, 2019, p. 171), as well as in the subject curriculum (2019, p. 54) and the *Primary Schools Curriculum* (2006, p. 35), only the name *predikat* is used.

Furthermore, two textbooks contain the dual names *izravni objekt / bliži objekt* (direct object / nearer object) and *neizravni objekt / dalji objekt* (indirect object / further object) (see *Table 6*). The same synonym pairs are used in Hudeček and Mihaljević (2019, p. 175), while Silić and Pranjković (2005, pp. 300–301) add the names *direktni objekt* and *indirektni objekt*. In Ham (2017, pp. 130–131), only the names *direktni objekt* and *indirektni objekt* are recorded, Težak and Babić (2016, p. 233) list synonym pairs *izravni objekt / direktni objekt* and *neizravni objekt / indirektni objekt*. The subject curriculum does not specify the names for the types of objects, and the *Primary School Curriculum* (2006, p. 42) lists only the names *neizravni objekt* and *izravni objekt*. It can be seen that the textbooks *Hrvatske jezične niti 7* and *Hrvatski za 7* accept the propositions contained in Hudeček and Ham (2019). Considering the general context of all textbooks, it was found that the names *direktni objekt* and *indirektni objekt* are not part of the contemporary textbook discourse.

Inconsistency was also observed in naming types of attributes. Three textbooks use the name *imenički atribut* (attributive noun) while the following three textbooks use the name *imenični atribut* (see *Table 6*). In the subject curriculum, these names are not mentioned, and the *Primary School Curriculum* (2006, p. 42) uses the name *imenički atribut*. When it comes to grammar books, Silić and Pranjković name the types of attributes regarding the concept of agreement, including both *sročni (kongruentni) atribut* (congruent attribute) and *nesročni (nekongruentni) atribut* (non-congruent attribute) (2005, pp. 309 and 311). In other grammars, there is a so-called paradigm with respect to parts of speech. Thus, Ham records the name *imenski atribut* (2017, p. 144), unlike Hudeček and Mihaljević who use *imenički atribut* (2019, p. 181). Težak and Babić (2016) do not specify the types of attributes, but in their grammar book they alternate between the names *imenički* and *imenični* (for example, *imenične dopune* (nominal complements), *imeničke/imenične zamjenice* (nominal pronouns)). We can say that a half of the textbooks follows the *Primary School Curriculum* (2006), regarding the names for the type of attribute without the agreement with the nominal word in gender, number, and case, while the other half follows the grammar book by Hudeček and Mihaljević. Accordingly, both names *imenički* and *imenični atribut* are used in textbooks, but *imenski atribut* is not accepted in contemporary textbooks.

Table 6.

Differences in the names of sentence parts in the analyzed textbooks

<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 7</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 7</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 7</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 7 (part 2)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 7</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 7</i>
predikat/prir ok (41)	predikat (60)	predikat (39)	predikat (43)	predikat (39)	predikat (57)
izravni objekt (46)	izravni/bliži objekt (74)	izravni/bliži objekt (48)	izravni objekt (67)	izravni objekt (52)	izravni objekt (65)
neizravni objekt (46)	neizravni/dal ji objekt (74)	neizravni/dal ji objekt (48)	neizravni objekt (67)	neizravni objekt (52)	neizravni objekt (66)
imenički atribut (56)	imenični atribut (84)	imenički atribut (57)	imenični atribut (84)	imenički atribut (59)	imenični atribut (73)

The type of subordinate sentence in which the dependent clause is embedded into the main clause in the place of an adverbial modifier of condition indicating a condition of performing the main clause action is called *pogodbena rečenica* (conditional sentence) in four textbooks, while in two textbooks there is a synonym pair *uvjetna rečenica / pogodbena rečenica* (see Table 7). In the *Primary School Curriculum*, this type of subordinate sentence is not recorded, while in the subject curriculum it is called *uvjetna rečenica* (2019, p. 172). Silić and Pranjković (2005, p. 347) and Hudeček and Mihaljević (2019, p. 210) refer to this type of sentence using a synonym pair that does not include the name *pogodbena*, but *uvjetna rečenica / kondicionalna rečenica*. In contrast, Težak and Babić (2016, p. 269) and Ham (2017, p. 166) use the name *pogodbene rečenice*. Finally, most contemporary textbooks follow the names found in Težak and Babić (2016) and Ham (2017), while two textbooks add to this synonymous pair also the name found in the subject curriculum.

Table 7.

Names for conditional sentence in the analyzed textbooks

<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 8</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 8</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 8</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 8 (part 2)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 8</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 8</i>
uvjetna/ pogodbena rečenica (110)	pogodbena/ uvjetna rečenica (173)	pogodbena rečenica (141)	pogodbena rečenica (102)	pogodbena rečenica (73)	pogodbena rečenica (100)

As for the word order in sentences, in the analyzed textbooks there are certain inconsistencies in the terminology. *Stilski obilježen red riječi* (free word order; stylistically marked word order) is used in one textbook along with the synonym *obrnuti red riječi* (reverse word order) which is not included in the other five textbooks, i.e. only *stilski obilježen red riječi* is used there (see Table 8). The subject curriculum (2019, p. 54) and the *Primary School Curriculum* (2006, p. 48) contain only the name *stilski obilježen red riječi*, which is also found in Hudeček and Mihaljević (2019, p. 220). Težak and Babić (2016, p. 285) use a sequence of synonyms including the names *obrnut*, *govornički (retorički)*, *obilježen* or *prigodni red riječi* (reverse, rhetorical, marked or occasional word order). In this case, we can notice uniformity with regard to the names in the *Curriculum* (2006), subject curriculum (2019) and Hudeček and Mihaljević (2019) as well as the high level of uniformity of this terminology in textbooks. The situation is more complex when naming fixed word order. Thus, two textbooks contain only the name *stilski neobilježen red riječi* (stylistically unmarked word order), in two textbooks the synonym *uobičajen red riječi* (common word order) is added, and in one textbook another synonym *gramatički red riječi* (grammatical word order) is used with the above-mentioned name. In contrast, one textbook contains all three names as a sequence of synonyms – *stilski neobilježen red riječi / gramatički red riječi / uobičajeni red riječi* (see Table 8). The *Primary School Curriculum* (2006, p. 48), the subject curriculum (2019, p. 54), and Hudeček and Mihaljević (2019, p. 220) here mention only *stilski neobilježen red riječi*, Težak and Babić (2016, p. 284) repeatedly use the sequence of synonyms *običan*, *neobilježen*, *neutralan red riječi* (common, unmarked, neutral word order). Consequently, the textbooks *Hrvatske jezične niti 7* and *Hrvatski za 7* follow the subject curriculum guidelines and the latest grammaticological determinants, while other textbooks contain synonyms. Mandatory word order in two textbooks is called *obvezan red riječi*, while in one textbook it is called *obvezatan red riječi*, and in the other three textbooks this name is not mentioned (see Table 8). It is not mentioned either in the analyzed grammar books, the *Primary School Curriculum* (2006), and the subject curriculum (2019).

Table 8.

Names for free (stylistically marked) and fixed (stylistically unmarked) word order in the analyzed textbooks

<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 7</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 7</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 7</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 7 (part 2)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 7</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 7</i>
stilski obilježen red riječi (75)	stilski obilježen red riječi (111)	stilski obilježen red riječi (75)	stilski obilježen / obnuti red riječi (115)	stilski obilježen red riječi (73)	stilski obilježen red riječi (73)
stilski neobilježen / gramatički red riječi (75)	stilski neobilježen red riječi (111)	stilski neobilježen red riječi (75)	stilski neobilježen/ uobičajen red riječi (115)	stilski neobilježen / gramatički / uobičajen red riječi (72)	stilski neobilježen / uobičajen red riječi (77)
obvezatan red riječi (77)	/	/	obvezan red riječi (116)	obvezan red riječi (74)	/

Other names are syntactically uniform in all textbooks, including: *glagolski predikat, imenski predikat, neoglagoljena rečenica, subjekt, jednostavna rečenica, jednostavna neproširena rečenica, jednostavna proširena rečenica, objekt, priložna oznaka, atribut, pridjevni atribut, atributni skup, apozicija, apozicijski skup, besubjektna rečenica, rečenica s neizrečenim subjektom, rečenica s više subjekata, preoblika, red riječi, složena rečenica, surečenica, veznička riječ, rečenični niz, nezavisnosložena rečenica, zavisnosložena rečenica, glavna surečenica, zavisna surečenica, sastavna rečenica, rastavna rečenica, suprotna rečenica, isključna rečenica, zaključna rečenica, predikatna rečenica, subjektna rečenica, objektna rečenica, atributna rečenica, priložna rečenica, uzročna rečenica, namjerna rečenica.*⁶

TERMS AT THE LEXICOLOGICAL LEVEL

When it comes to names related to the linguistic diversity of the Croatian language, past plans and programs and the subject curriculum differ in the use of the name *književni jezik* (literary language), which in the Croatian tradition commonly means also the standard language.⁷ Thus, in the *Primary School Curriculum*, the name *standardni jezik* (standard language) is introduced only in grade 8 (2006, p. 47), and

⁶ Verbal predicate, nominal predicate, nonverbal sentence, subject, simple sentence, simple unexpanded sentence, simple expanded sentence, object, adverbial modifier, attribute, attributive adjective, attributive phrase, apposition, appositive phrase, subjectless sentence, unspoken subject sentence, multiple subjects sentence, transformation, word order, complex sentence, clause, linking word, sentence sequence, coordinated sentence, subordinate sentence, main clause, dependent clause, compound sentence, alternative sentence, adversative sentence, exclusive sentence, conclusive sentence, predicate sentence, subject sentence, object sentence, attribute sentence, adverbial sentence, conditional sentence, intentional sentence.

⁷ Cf. for example: “Temelj je školskoga predmeta koji se zove hrvatski jezik zajednički jezik svih Hrvata, tj. književni ili standardni hrvatski jezik.” (“The basis of the school subject called Croatian language is the common language of all Croats, i.e. the literary or standard Croatian language.”) (Težak, 1996, p. 87)

in the previous grades, only *književni jezik* is mentioned (2006, pp. 33, 35). In the subject curriculum, only the name *standardni jezik* is used, which is accepted in all analyzed textbooks. The term *manjinski jezik* (minority language), which is introduced in the old and new curricula in grade 5, is used under this name in four textbooks, while two textbooks mention the name *jezik nacionalne manjine* (national minority language) (see *Table 9*).

Table 9.

The names minority language and national minority language

<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 5</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 5</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 5</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 5 (part 1)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 5</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 5</i>
jezik	manjinski	manjinski	manjinski	jezik	manjinski
nacionalne manjine (99)	jezik (18)	jezik (36)	jezik (58)	nacionalne manjine (10)	jezik (11)

In the unit *Word Relationships* of the *Primary School Curriculum*, the key terms are *istoznačnice*, *bliskoznačnice*, and *suprotnice* (synonyms, near-synonyms, and antonyms) (2006, p. 44). Previously used terms were *sinonimi* and *antonimi* (synonyms and antonyms) (Jelaska, 2007), which are however mentioned in the subject curriculum (2019, p. 61). Namely, in Croatian lexicological practice, it is common to divide synonyms into *istoznačnice* and *bliskoznačnice* (Jelaska, 2007), but some scholars, such as Branka Tafra, disagree, emphasizing that it is necessary to distinguish synonymy as a paradigmatic lexical-semantic relationship from synonymy at the syntagmatic level, rejecting the existence of absolute synonyms and near-synonyms as a type of synonymy (cf. Tafra, 1996, 2003, 2018). Jelaska (2007) argues that the goal of using Croatian, semantically more transparent names would be to notice, understand, and practically master different relationships between words, acquiring basic knowledge that will be complemented by foreign names, terms, and divisions.

In the analyzed textbooks, the division of synonyms into *istoznačnice* and *bliskoznačnice* prevails, i.e. five of the six textbooks for grade 8 contain such division and include the above names (see *Table 10*). In two of these textbooks, *Hrvatska krijesnica* and *Volim hrvatski*, there is a synonym pair of these two terms, where the second component contains an attributive syntagm: *istoznačnice / potpuni sinonimi* (synonyms / absolute synonyms) and *bliskoznačnice / djelomični sinonimi* (near-synonyms / partial synonyms). In one textbook, *Hrvatske jezične niti*, the division of synonyms is not recorded, but the name *sinonim* is equated with the name *istoznačnica*, not following the traditional division of synonyms in Croatian into *istoznačnice* and *bliskoznačnice* and rejecting the assumption of non-existence of absolute synonymy, including the term *istoznačnica*.

All six textbooks for grade 8 use the name *antonimi/suprotnice* (antonyms/opposites) as a synonymous pair, but the textbooks differ in giving preference to either Croatian or foreign name. In three of the six textbooks, the recommended Croatian name *suprotnice* is used, while the other three textbooks offer international name *antonimi* (see *Table 10*), which reflects the inconsistency in their use in education documents along with the differences in linguistic considerations on the use of Croatian names and international names. In this case, obviously one part of the textbooks relies on the subject curriculum that uses the name *antonimi* (2019, p. 61), and the other part on the *Primary School Curriculum* that uses *suprotnice* (2006, p. 44). Certainly, in the given examples, inconsistency can be noticed in lexicological terminology at the level of the division of synonyms and dilemmas about the use of the Croatian name or loanword, which is reflected in the textbook discourse as well.

Table 10.*Names for synonyms and antonyms in the analyzed textbooks*

<i>Hrvatska kriješnica 8</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 8</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 8</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 8 (part 2)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 8</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 8</i>
istoznačnice, potpuni sinonimi (143)	istoznačnice, sinonimi (18)	istoznačnice (19)	istoznačnice (137)	istoznačnice (82)	istoznačnice, potpuni sinonimi (109)
bliskoznačnice, djelomični sinonimi (143)	/	bliskoznačnice (19)	bliskoznačnice (138)	bliskoznačnice (82)	bliskoznačnice, djelomični sinonimi (109)
antonimi, suprotnice (143)	suprotnice, antonimi (20)	suprotnice, antonimi (20)	suprotnice, antonimi (139)	suprotnice, antonimi (82)	antonimi, suprotnice (109)

The observed inconsistency is confirmed by the use of the synonym pair *međunarodnica/internacionalizam* (internationalism), which is used in the textbook *Volim hrvatski 8*. Three textbooks contain the synonym pair *europaizam/internacionalizam* (Europeanism/internationalism), one textbook contains only the name *internacionalizam*, and in one textbook the name for this term is missing (see *Table 11*). Five textbooks also mention the synonym pair *novotvorenice* and *neologizam* (neologism), while in the textbook *Naš hrvatski 8* only the name *neologizam* is represented (see *Table 11*).

Table 11.*Names for internationalisms, Europeanisms, and neologisms in the analyzed textbooks*

<i>Hrvatska kriješnica 8</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 8</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 8</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 8 (part 2)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 8</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 8</i>
europaizam/internacionalizam (138)	europaizam/internacionalizam (27)	internacionalizam (29)	europaizam/internacionalizam (128)	/	međunarodnica/internacionalizam (105)
novotvorenica/neologizam (139)	novotvorenica/neologizam (32)	neologizam/novotvorenica (30)	novotvorenica/neologizam (139)	neologizam (95)	novotvorenica/neologizam (106)

In all analyzed textbooks, the following names are uniform at the lexicological level: *drugi jezik, službeni jezik, dvojezičnost, zavičajni govor, mjesni govor, hrvatski standardni jezik, razgovorni jezik,*

*jednorječno ime, višerječno ime, materinski jezik, narječje, čakavsko narječje, štokavsko narječje, kajkavsko narječje, posuđenica, tuđica, usvojenica, pleonazam, frazem.*⁸

TERMS AT THE ORTHOGRAPHICAL LEVEL

As for the names related to Croatian orthography used in primary school textbooks, in the compared orthography and spelling books the differences have been noticed in the use of the names *dvotočje* and *trotočje* / *dvotočka* and *trotočka*, *točka sa zarezom* and *točka-zarez*, *apostrof* and *izostavnik* (colon, three dots, semicolon, apostrophe). Moreover, in the orthography and spelling book published by the Institute of Croatian Language and Linguistics (Jozić, 2013), a new name was introduced to designate abbreviations distinguishing *pokrate* from *kratice*, a term used in previous orthography and spelling books, which did not make this distinction.

In the Croatian linguistic tradition, there is an inconsistency in the use of the names *dvotočje/dvotočka* (:) and *trotočje/trotočka* (...) (Bagdasarov 2008) because there is no generally accepted normative position regarding numerical expressions ending with a collective suffix *-je* which, among others, include both *dvotočje* and *trotočje* (Hudeček and Raguž, 1993).

These variants in the names can be seen in Vitezović's dictionary published at the end of the 17th century, which records the names *dvotočje* and today's unusual form *dvojtočka* (Putanec, 1976) as a synonymous pair. This dilemma continued in contemporary Croatian orthography and spelling books. Thus, in *Hrvatski školski pravopis* (2005) by Babić-Ham-Moguš and *Hrvatski pravopis usklađen sa zaključcima Vijeća za normu hrvatskoga standardnog jezika* (2010) by Babić-Moguš, the terms *dvotočje* and *trotočje* are used, while *Hrvatski pravopis* (2008) by Lada Badurina, Ivan Marković, and Krešimir Mićanović and *Hrvatski pravopis* (Jozić, 2013) use the names *dvotočka* and *trotočka*. The same names are used in official education policies documents and in the orthography and spelling books approved for use in schools. The mentioned manual by Babić-Ham-Moguš was once approved for use in schools, consequently the names *dvotočje* and *trotočje* were used in the *Primary School Curriculum* (2006, p. 40), while the subject curriculum uses the names *dvotočka* and *trotočka* (2019, p. 155), which is in line with the currently approved orthography and spelling book published by the Institute of Croatian Language and Linguistics for school use. In all the analyzed textbooks, only the names *dvotočka* and *trotočka* are used (see Table 12), and the previously mentioned dilemma is uniform at least in contemporary school practice.

Semicolon (;) in older orthography and spelling books is mostly called *točka-zarez*, *točka sa zarezom*, and *točka i zarez* (cf. Mamić and Lukenda, 1992), while newer manuals use *točka sa zarezom* (Babić, Ham, and Moguš, 2005, p. 13; Babić and Moguš, 2010, p. 111; Jozić, 2013, p. 100), which is also used in the subject curriculum (2019, p. 155). On the other hand, Badurina, Marković, and Mićanović (2008, p. 62) use the name *točka-zarez*. All textbooks analyzed here follow the latest orthography currents and use the name *točka sa zarezom* (see Table 12).

Table 12.

Uniform names for orthographic punctuation marks [:], [...] and [;]

<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 6</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 6</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 6</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 6 (part 1)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 6</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 6</i>
dvotočka (105)	dvotočka (146)	dvotočka (93)	dvotočka (23)	dvotočka (70)	dvotočka (19)

⁸ Second language, official language, bilingualism, native speech, local speech, Croatian standard language, colloquial language, one-word name, multi-word name, mother tongue, dialect, Chakavian dialect, Shtokavian dialect, Kajkavian dialect, loanword, not-fully-adapted loanword, fully-adapted loanword, pleonasm, phraseme.

trotočka (105)	trotočka (146)	trotočka (93)	trotočka (23)	trotočka (70)	trotočka (20)
točka sa zarezmom (105)	točka sa zarezmom (146)	točka sa zarezmom (93)	točka sa zarezmom (23)	točka sa zarezmom (70)	točka sa zarezmom (21)

Our orthographic tradition records also a double name for an apostrophe ('). In older orthographies, the use of the name *apostrof* is common (cf. Mamić and Lukenda, 1992), while *izostavnik* is commonly used in newer manuals (Babić, Ham and Moguš, 2005, p. 13; Babić and Moguš, 2010, p. 111; Jozić, 2013, p. 110) as well as in the subject curriculum (2019, p. 171) and the *Primary School Curriculum* (2006, p. 39). Badurina, Marković, and Mićanović use the recommended name *apostrof* along with the allowed name *izostavnik* (2008, p. 105). In two analyzed textbooks, only the Croatian name *izostavnik* is recorded, in three of them the Croatian name is preferred, along with the name *apostrof*, while one textbook, *Hrvatski za 8*, does not mention this punctuation mark (see *Table 13*).

Table 13.

Names for the orthographic punctuation mark [']

<i>Hrvatska krijesnica 8</i>	<i>Hrvatske jezične niti 8</i>	<i>Hrvatski za 8</i>	<i>Hrvatski bez granica 8 (part 1)</i>	<i>Naš hrvatski 8</i>	<i>Volim hrvatski 8</i>
izostavnik/ apostrof (130)	izostavnik/ apostrof (196)	/	izostavnik (29)	izostavnik (103)	izostavnik/ apostrof (34)

The analyzed textbooks as well as the subject curriculum (2019, p. 163) accept the distinction between *kratice* and *pokrate* (contractions vs. initialisms and acronyms) introduced in the manual published by the Institute of Croatian Language and Linguistics, which distinguishes *kratice* – formed by abbreviating one or more words, not capitalized, not declinable, and written with a full stop as a rule (Jozic, 2013, p. 76) – from *pokrate*, which are capitalized and declinable, and written without a full stop, except for Latin borrowed ones (Jozic, 2013, p. 78). In accordance with the above semantic difference, the textbooks use both names.

It can therefore be concluded that in all analyzed textbooks the following punctuation mark names are uniform: *dvotočka, trotočka, točka sa zarezmom, točka, zarez, zgrade, navodnici, polunavodnici, crtica, spojnica, kosa crta, kratice, pokrate, upitnik, uskličnik, upitnik s uskličnikom, uskličnik s upitnikom*.⁹

CONCLUSION

The paper presents the first phase of the research on linguistic terminology used in contemporary textbooks of the Croatian language. The research was conducted on primary school textbooks for grades

⁹ Colon, three dots, semicolon, dot, comma, parentheses, quotation marks, single quotation marks, hyphen, dash, slash, abbreviations (contractions vs. initialisms and acronyms), question mark, exclamation mark, question mark with exclamation mark, exclamation mark with question mark.

5–8, which were developed in line with the requirements of the 2019 *National Curriculum*. A much higher level of uniformity has been found in the use of the linguistic terms at all language levels in the analyzed textbooks than in the previous textbooks, yet a complete uniformity has not been achieved. Regarding the phonological level, despite the fact that the term *jekavski govor* (Jekavian speech) was accepted in professional literature, most textbooks contain the older name (*i*)*jekavski govor* ((I)jekavian speech). At the morphological level, the lack of uniformity is seen in the terms *glagolska osoba* and *glagolsko lice* used to name the category of verbal person; in contrast to the subject curriculum based on which the textbooks were made, the use of the name *glagolska osoba* predominates. Lack of uniformity is also seen in the use of one-word names for speaker/interlocutor/non-speaker participating in a communication situation. At the syntactic level, we have noticed that the names *imenički/imenični/imenski atribut* are used to denote an attributive noun in here compared Croatian grammars, while the name *imenski atribut* is not used in textbooks, and the use of both names *imenički* and *imenični atribut* has been confirmed. Only two textbooks use the name *uvjetna rečenica* (conditional sentence), which is in line with grammar books by Silić and Pranjković and by Hudeček and Mihaljević and is also used in the subject curriculum. In contrast, most textbooks use the name *pogodbena rečenica*. At the lexicological level, textbooks contain differences primarily in using either Croatian or foreign names in naming semantic relations between words (*istoznačnice*, *bliskoznačnice*, *sinonimi* meaning synonyms), and in giving preference to either Croatian word or loanword (*suprotnice/antonimi*; *internacionalizmi/europeizmi/međunarodnice*; *novotvorenice/neologizmi*) (*antonyms*; *internationalisms/Europeanisms*; *neologisms*). With some less pronounced exceptions, it has been found that textbooks do not follow the subject curriculum regarding most of the shown double and/or different names, which leads to the conclusion that it is hard to change the nomenclature paradigm in the textbook discourse as it does not readily accept all relevant changes. On the other hand, the highest degree of textbooks consistency was achieved at the orthographical level. The names are almost completely uniform in the analyzed textbooks, in accordance with the nomenclature solutions presented in the orthography and spelling book *Hrvatski pravopis* published by the Institute of Croatian Language and Linguistics, which are also accepted in the subject curriculum.

This research opened the question of (the lack of) uniformity of linguistic terms in contemporary textbooks of the Croatian language. A complete insight into the discussed issues will be gained after the second phase of the research which will include the corpus of high school textbooks.

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